

Synthesis and Structural Studies of Metal Complexes of 6-Methyl-2-Amino Benzothiazole and 2-Methyl Benzimidazole

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Complexes of the types MLX_2 , ML_2X_2 , ML_4X_2 [$M = Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Fe(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II)$; $L = 6\text{-methyl-2-amino benzothiazole}$; $X = I, NCS, OAc$] and mixed ligand complexes of the general formula $ML_2L'X_2$ [$M = Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II)$; $L' = 2\text{-methyl benzimidazole}$; $X = Cl, I, Br, NCS$] have been prepared and characterised on the basis of analytical, magnetic moment, molar conductance, electronic and ir spectral data. The mixed ligand complexes have six coordinated octahedral configuration.

LITERATURE reveals that substituted benzothiazoles have analytical and biological¹⁻⁴ importance.

Complexes of 2-amino benzothiazole, substituted benzothiazole⁵⁻⁸ and mixed ligand complexes⁹⁻¹² have been reported earlier. Some anionic complexes of Zn(II) and Cd(II) exhibiting unusual coordination were also reported earlier¹³. The nitrogen donor ligand, imidazole, is significant as a ligand towards transition metals because of its biological activity¹⁴. It was, therefore, considered worthwhile to investigate the metal complexes of the above mentioned ligand.

Experimental

The chemicals used in this study were B.D.H. products. 6-Methyl-2-amino benzothiazole was prepared by the method of Hugershoff¹⁵.

The MLX_2 , ML_2X_2 and ML_4X_2 types of complexes were prepared by mixing the hot ethanolic solutions of metal iodide or acetate and the ligand in 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 4 (metal : ligand) molar ratio, respectively except for Cd(II) and Hg(II) where the solvent used was acetone. The resulting mixtures were refluxed for 3-4 hr and the coloured solutions were evaporated to dryness, washed with distilled water and 10% alcohol and dried *in vacuo* over anhydrous calcium chloride.

$CoL_2(OAc)_2$ complex was prepared by mixing the hot ethanolic solution of cobalt acetate and the ligand in 1 : 2 molar ratio and refluxing for 2-3 hr. $CoL_2(NCS)_2$, $FeL_2(NCS)_2$, $MnL_2(NCS)_2$, $ZnL_4(NCS)_2$ and $CdL_4(NCS)_2$ were isolated accordingly by mixing the hot ethanolic solutions of metal chloride and ammonium thiocyanate, and ligand in 1 : 2 and 1 : 4 molar ratio.

$ML_2L'X_2$ [$M = Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II)$; $X = Cl, Br, NCS$] complexes were prepared by refluxing ML_2X_2 and 2-methyl benzimidazole in 1 : 2 molar

ratio in acetone for 3 hr. The solids were recovered as stated above.

Molar conductance of the complexes in methanol, acetone and chloroform ($10^{-3} M$) was measured in WTW conductivity meter. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out at room temperature on Cahn electrobalance using $Hg[Co(NCS)_4]$ as calibrant. Diamagnetic corrections were applied by the method outlined by Figgis and Lewis¹⁶. All the complexes were analysed for metals using standard procedures¹⁷. The analytical data of the complexes showed agreement between the experimental and the theoretical values.

The electronic spectra of the complexes were recorded on Cary-14 and VSU-2Ph spectrophotometers. The ir spectra were recorded in KBr and nujol mulls on Perkin Elmer spectrophotometers, model 621 and 720.

Results and Discussion

The non-electrolytic¹⁸ nature of the complexes is shown by the low molar conductances values (0.02-30.58 mhos $cm^2/mole$).

The magnetic moments indicate square planar geometry for $CuLI_2$, $CuL(NCS)_2$ and $NiLI_2$. The magnetic moments of tetrahedral Fe(II) complexes are expected to be about 5.1 B.M.¹⁹, whereas those of regular octahedral species are about 5.5 B.M. The room temperature magnetic moment measured for $FeL_2(NCS)_2$ is 5.4 B.M. which is reasonable for octahedral complex. These data, however, are not conclusive as in some cases the moments for tetrahedral species approach 5.4 B.M. e.g. $[FeCl_4]^{2-}$ ²⁰. The magnetic moments of all the Co(II) complexes are in the range 4.4-4.8 B.M., which is normally observed for tetrahedral Co(II) complexes²¹ and confirm tetrahedral geometry in the present cases. The magnetic moments of Mn(II) complexes

correspond to five unpaired electrons and indicate tetrahedral geometry. The diamagnetic ML_2X_2 [$M=Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II)$] complexes show sp^3 type of hybridization.

$NiLi_2$ complex assumes D_4h symmetry²²⁻²⁴ with the ligand fields $\nu_1=15582$, $\nu_2=19952$, $\nu_3=22174$ cm^{-1} which may be attributed to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$, 1E_g , ${}^1B_{1g}$ transitions, respectively.

$CoLi_2$, $CoL_2(OAc)_2$ and $CoL_2(NCS)_2$ show two bands at 5279, 5394 and 5410 cm^{-1} (ν_2) and 15111, 15584 and 15610 cm^{-1} (ν_3), assigned to the ${}^4A_2 \rightarrow {}^4T_1(F)$, ${}^4T_1(P)$ transitions, respectively and are characteristics of $Co(II)$ ion in the tetrahedral environment²⁵. Using the values of ν_2 and ν_3 , 10 D_q and B' were calculated by the equation given by Drag²⁶, for the tetrahedral $Co(II)$ complexes. The values of $10Dq$, B' , β' , ν_2/ν_1 , λ' , ξ_3d and LFSE of all the three complexes, calculated from the above transitions, come out to be 3413.2 cm^{-1} , 676.7 cm^{-1} , 0.69, 30.24%, 1.55, 118.7 cm^{-1} , 356.3 cm^{-1} , 48.96 kJ/mole; 3482 cm^{-1} , 702.1 cm^{-1} , 0.72, 27.61%. 1.55, -125.6 cm^{-1} , 376.9 cm^{-1} , 49.95 kJ/mole; 3483.1 cm^{-1} , 704.7 cm^{-1} , 0.71, 27.36%, 1.55, -116.7 cm^{-1} , 350.1 cm^{-1} and 49.97 kJ/mole, respectively.

$CuLi_2$ and $CuL(NCS)_2$ yield one broad band at 17182 and 17452 cm^{-1} , respectively which are supposed to be composite envelope of the three transitions ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$, ${}^2B_{2g}$, ${}^2E_{1g}$. The $10Dq$, λ' , ξ_3d and LFSE values of these complexes come out to be 17182 cm^{-1} , -198.6 cm^{-1} , 198.6 cm^{-1} , 123.24 kJ/mole; 17452 cm^{-1} , -252.2 cm^{-1} , 252.2 cm^{-1} and 125.2 kJ/mole, respectively. These data suggest square planar configuration²³⁻²⁴ of the $Cu(II)$ complexes.

The ir spectrum of the ligand²⁷ shows $\nu_{as}(NH)$, $\nu_s(NH)$, $\nu(C=N)$, δNH , $\rho_r(NH_2)$ and $\rho_w(NH_2)$ peaks at 3425, 3315, 1550, 1650, 1120 and 760 cm^{-1} , respectively. The $\nu(C-S-C)$ band¹⁹ is obtained at 815 cm^{-1} .

In all the complexes there is a considerable lowering in the $\nu_{as}(NH)$ (3300-3410 cm^{-1}), $\nu_s(NH)$ (3175-3300 cm^{-1}), $\delta(HNH)$ (1600-1635 cm^{-1}), $\rho_r(NH_2)$ (1090-1120 cm^{-1}) and $\rho_w(NH_2)$ (715-735 cm^{-1}) indicating that the coordination is through exocyclic NH_2 group. The $\nu(C-S-C)$ and $\nu(C=N)$ (cyclic) remain unchanged showing the absence of coordination through ring sulphur and $C=N$ groups.

Certain correlations between νCN and νCS modes and the type of thiocyanate bonding have been made^{28,29} in the ir spectrum of the metal complexes containing coordinated thiocyanate groups. For $M-NCS$ bonding νCN and νCS appear to fall in the $\sim 2080-2040$ and $860-780$ cm^{-1} ranges, respectively. The corresponding ranges for $M-SCN$ bonding are $\sim 2120-2080$ and $720-680$ cm^{-1} . For bridging thiocyanate groups, $M-SCN-M$ the νCN falls in a broader and generally higher range than $M-NCS$ while the νCS usually occurs at intermediate frequencies. In the ionic thiocyanate, νCN occurs at ~ 1963 cm^{-1} and νCS at ~ 963 cm^{-1} .

In the ir spectrum of $CuL(NCS)_2$, the νCN occurs at 2090 cm^{-1} and νCS at 755 cm^{-1} , indicative of bridging thiocyanate group. The δNCS could not be recorded due to the limitation of the range of the instrument used.

The νCN occurs at 2075, 2080, 2085 and 2080 cm^{-1} in the ir spectrum of $CoL_2(NCS)_2$, $MnL_2(NCS)_2$, $ZnL_4(NCS)_2$ indicative of $M-NCS$ bonding³⁰.

In $FeL_2(NCS)_2$, the νCN , νCS and δNCS occur at 2040, 850 and 475 cm^{-1} , respectively showing $M-NCS$ bonding.

The νCN and νCS modes occur at 2075 and 850 cm^{-1} for $ZnL_2L'_2(NCS)_2$ and at 2080 and 855 cm^{-1} for $CdL_2L'_2(NCS)_2$ complexes.

The non-ligand bands occurring in the ir spectra of $NiLi_2$ and $FeL_2(NCS)_2$ at 350 and 355 cm^{-1} may tentatively be assigned to $\nu(M-N)$ mode³⁰.

The carboxylates²⁹ give a strong asymmetric stretching band near 1650-1550 cm^{-1} and a weaker symmetrical stretching band near 1400 cm^{-1} . The $CoL_2(OAc)_2$ shows two sharp peaks at 1570 and

1395 cm^{-1} , assignable to $\nu_{as} \left(\begin{array}{c} O \\ \diagdown \\ C \\ \diagup \\ O \end{array} \right)$ and $\nu_s \left(\begin{array}{c} O \\ \diagdown \\ C \\ \diagup \\ O \end{array} \right)$ vibrations.

The mixed ligand complexes show additional (N-H) bending and stretching frequencies at 1360-1400 and 3340-3350 cm^{-1} , respectively indicating that the 2-methyl benzimidazole is coordinated through tertiary nitrogen atom, as confirmed earlier²¹ by X-ray structural studies.

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